

Sustain Sahel

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I. Introduction

The SustainSahel project website, built by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, is the central collection and information point for all materials generated in the project and contains all relevant information about the project and its outcomes. The objective has been defined: To provide a portal via which all specialist and lay audiences can view the project mission, progress and results and access and download information as required. It is the project's window to the world regarding project plans, actions, progress, achievements and publications. It is in constant development in collaboration with project partners needs. The website is continuously updated with information, knowledge and materials created in SustainSahel.

According to the grant agreement, the following items are to be made available on the website:

- › Homepage
- › Project news
- › Video, visual and oral materials
- › Social media accounts
- › Project resources, information and material
- › Publications
- › E-news – issued three times annually (15 times in total)

These items aim to provide two-way engagement with targeted and priority stakeholders at local, national, regional, European and international levels. The project website (www.sustainsahel.net), featured in both English and French, went online in January 2021.

The following pages explain the websites' rationale, show its current status and consider ideas for further developing the SustainSahel website as the knowledge hub for the project, providing access for all to its materials and results.

2. Website features, contents and plans

2.1 Website features

2.1.1 Visual identity

The SustainSahel logo is featured prominently on every subpage's top left corner and is fixed to the top of the page when scrolling down. The EU flag with project information is fixed on the upper right of the website. Additionally, the website uses the same colour pattern that can be found in the logo (see D8.5). These colours visually represent the Sahel region, and therefore the project (Figure 1). Maintaining the same colour scheme across all outlets (website, social media channels, publications, etc.) strengthens the logo and project's visual identity.

Figure 1. Visual identity on SustainSahel website.

2.1.2 Responsive design

A responsive website means that it adjusts its margins to the screen size or the web browser used. The SustainSahel project's website is responsive – i.e. the project website is mobile friendly and can be viewed easily on smartphones and other devices.

2.1.3 Integration of Google Maps

Google Maps is integrated on the project website to show the locations of the project partners and the project areas. The map is available in 'map' or 'satellite' view, and points of interest for the project are displayed and linked to further information. This special feature may be used for further purposes on the website.

2.1.4 News archiving

The project website contains a feature for the automatic archiving of news. News can also be made available/archived by theme. For instance, all news relating to shrubs or livestock could be made available on the website's related section.

Action 1: Add project-related themes to the news archive system to allow further categorisation.

2.1.5 Integration of SustainSahel social media accounts

The Sustain Sahel project has six social media accounts:

1. Twitter: www.twitter.com/SustainSahelEU
2. Facebook: www.facebook.com/sustainsaheleu
3. Instagram: www.instagram.com/sustainsaheleu
4. YouTube: www.youtube.com/channel/xxx
5. ResearchGate: www.researchgate.net/project/SustainSAHEL
6. LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/sustain-sahel-eu

These accounts were created in January 2021. The accounts contain posts, videos, and publications produced within the Sustain Sahel project (i.e. WP 8 leader MINERVA); related posts from project partners social media accounts are shared on the project's accounts. The Sustain Sahel Twitter, Facebook, and Youtube accounts are fully integrated into the project website, located on the right hand side of the footer.

2.1.6 Language capabilities – English and French

The website's contents are initially written in English; however, DeepL Translator is integrated and utilised to translate the website, and all of its features, into French. Although translation programs have developed immensely in recent years, we recognise that translations are not perfect. That's why we have asked partners to check the website for language errors in French periodically.

Ongoing task 1: Remind partners annually to review the website for language errors.

2.2 Website current contents, structure and focus

The initial website technical structure and aesthetics have been designed and developed by FiBL and Minerva. Structurally, the website includes background, project overview, specific information about each work package, project partners, areas, and contact information. In addition to project information, the website aims to cater to diverse stakeholders' interests, from the broader public to policy-players at national, European, and international levels, to farmers and their advisers to actors across the appropriate agricultural value chains. The website's current contents, particularly the descriptions of partner organisations and project areas, were written in close collaboration with relevant partners.

The initial website is currently undergoing further development and will be under continuous review. An editorial schedule is being created to ensure that all partners contribute content for the website, keeping it up-to-date and engaging, supporting efforts to widen the project's reputation and influence content as the project develops. Tailored and relevant content will be provided through the website and other dissemination outlets.

Figure 2. SustainSahel website homepage, February 2021.

Action 2: Complete editorial and content creation schedule integrating partners into the websites' further development.

2.2.1 Homepage – www.sustainsahel.net

The homepage contains (Figure 2)

- A short description of the SustainSahel project;
- An infobox about SustainSahel;
- Photo banner linking to other pages of the website;
- SustainSahel news

Any event or further outreach activities of the partners will also be announced on the homepage (and shared on social media and via other relevant channels).

The website and social media 'kick-off' took place on February 18th upon the completion of the kick-off photo competition, in which project partners were encouraged to submit their photos. Six winners were chosen by an expert board and are featured as the first news item and on the banner of the homepage. Partners have also been encouraged to review the website regularly, with many already providing useful suggestions.

Ongoing task 2: Keep website alive with news and add or change pictures when new images become available

2.2.2 About – www.sustainsahel.net/about

The 'About' page of the SustainSahel website provides information about the project and its aims, project consortium, funding bodies, internal links to related projects and a short description of all work packages. The work package descriptions were developed in collaboration with the work package leader and co-leader. These descriptions briefly explain their aims and methods and provide the work package leader and co-leader contact information.

A general overview and history of the Sahel region with insights provided as to the needs of the area and the purpose and expected outcomes from the project's work is needed. Project partners are already equipped with the knowledge necessary to create this page and be asked to provide information and appropriate imagery to saturate this page.

Action 3: Develop a description of the Sahel region in collaboration with project partners with a particular focus on Western Sahel where the project is operational.

2.2.3 Partners – www.sustainsahel.net/partners

For the launch of the website in February 2021, the list of partners was ready. The main 'Partners' page includes an integrated map providing viewers with an overview of the partners' locations, available in 'map' or 'satellite' view (Figure 3). When clicking on a flag, the information on the individual partners/partner pages appears and is linked to the partners' description page, where a brief description of the institution, the partners' logos, their role in the project, a list of the key people involved and their contact information are provided.

Ongoing task 3: Remind partners annually to check their institutions' descriptions and contacts and send updates.

2.2.4 Areas – www.sustainsahel.net/areas

The 'Areas' page was ready for the kick-off in February 2021 but remains flexible for further development in the near future. On this page, the three areas where the project work is focused are presented. The main 'Areas' page features a brief description of the research approach as well as an interactive Google Map, available in 'map' or 'satellite' view, showing the location of each focus area.

The Areas page is structured according to the countries in focus, namely Senegal, Mali and Burkina Faso. Each country has a subpage that features a short description, relevant photos taken by partners and links to further subpages for each study area located in that country. On these study area subpages, each study area is described in more detail relating to the site's history, natural ecosystem features, land management system and what is planned for experimentation. More specific technical information about the methods implemented at each study area will be added as the information becomes available. The specific subpages for each study area will soon feature images taken at the sites.

Action 4: Coordinate with partners to obtain photos for each project area – to be featured on the website.

Ongoing task 4: List relevant news items, once they become available, on related subpages within the 'Areas' page.

Ongoing task 5: Keep information related to experiments up-to-date.

2.2.5 Communications – www.sustainsahel.net/communications

The 'Communications' section of the website is dedicated to linking viewers to current and archived news, upcoming events, project outputs, social media platforms as well as a featured photo gallery. An events page will highlight the project's events and external events and initiatives related to the project's objectives and ambition being organised by associated projects and organisations.

Action 5: Create an events page.

The photo gallery (Figure 3) now features the winning images from the kick-off photo competition. The gallery will be developed further as more images are received from project partners. Photographers who have shared their images (via SharePoint) for the project retain ownership of the material, but agree that the material can be made public in project communications, this includes the project website, social media platforms and press releases. Photographers are responsible for verbally receiving permission from identifiable individuals. Each photo is accompanied by a short description including the location and a credit to the photographer.

Ongoing task 6: Develop photo gallery further and keep up-to-date with new photos.

In the future, a registration form will be available to subscribe to the project e-newsletter, issued three times annually (15 times in total). The e-news, provided in French and English, will be provided for contacts on the database enabling the project to keep in touch directly with all interested parties. Contacts will be recruited via the website, collaborations and promotions with project and external partners and permissions secured via direct contact and request.

The growing database will only hold enough personal details to enable the sending of the e-news and will be GDPR compliant. Each e-news will carry a clear message to 'unsubscribe' with all such requests being actioned within 7 working days of receipt. All newsletters will be archived on the website.

Figure 3. SustainSahel website photo gallery, February 2021.

Action 6: Create a page and registration form for e-newsletters, as well as an archive.

As the project progresses, videos and podcasts will be secured and presented on this page. Partners from each field site will be closely involved in the development of this content.

Action 7: Create a page for videos and podcasts as they become available.

The 'social media' subpage links users to the project's profiles on Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Research Gate, LinkedIn and YouTube. The 'publications' subpage leads to the SustainSahel community on Zenodo.org, where all SustainSahel outputs created during the project duration are stored. Additionally, selected publications will be highlighted on the SustainSahel website homepage as a news item and/or banner.

By storing and publishing (after the embargo period) the scientific publications and other output on ZENODO, SustainSahel ensures that bibliographic metadata are included such as the funding body, the name of the action, acronym and grant number (already predefined in ZENODO), the publication date, and a persistent identifier. Via ZENODO, the publications are automatically stored on OpenAIRE, the European Union's electronic gateway for peer-reviewed articles and other important publications (www.openaire.eu).

2.2.6 Impressum/Contact – www.sustainsahel.net/impressum-contact

The 'impressum / contact' page shows the project's contact addresses and website, the disclaimer and acknowledgement for the European Union and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), and the privacy policy.

The contents of this website are owned by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) and protected by copyright law. According to the General Data Protection Regulation, the data protection officer is Lisa Haller from FiBL Europe.

All legal requirements that must be followed (e.g. provision of information about the privacy policy, imprint information, etc.) have been taken into account during the creation of the website. The website uses SSL encryption to eliminate the transmission of personal data and protect all confidential content.

2.2.7 Focus on collaboration and inclusion

Since the website creates an image for the project, gender and diversity inclusions will always be at the forefront. Consideration will be given throughout to represent diversity and inclusion with particular attention to content and imagery of women and youth, vital groups with which the project must engage. The imagery on the project's website depicts a range of landscape and farming scenes from the Sahel region, with the goal of incorporating many more 'on the ground' images and photographs taken by the project team in Africa in galleries featured on various sections of the website.

Ongoing task 7: Develop the website keeping inclusion - for gender, diversity and age – as the focus.

3. Actions and ongoing tasks

3.1 Actions needed for future development

In the coming months, the actions outlined in previous chapters will be implemented:

- › Action 1: Add project-related themes to the news archive system to allow further categorisation.
- › Action 2: Complete editorial and content creation schedule integrating partners into the websites' further development.
- › Action 3: Develop a description of the Sahel region in collaboration with project partners.
- › Action 4: Coordinate with partners to obtain photos for each project area – to be featured on the website.
- › Action 5: Create an events page.
- › Action 6: Create a page and registration form for e-newsletters.
- › Action 7: Create a page for videos and podcasts as they become available.

Should new needs arise, these actions will be adapted accordingly. These actions will be finalised by M9.

3.2 Ongoing tasks

In previous chapters ongoing tasks were highlighted and include:

- › Ongoing task 1: Remind partners annually to review the website for language errors.
- › Ongoing task 2: Keep website alive with news and add or change pictures when new images come.
- › Ongoing task 3: Remind partners annually to check their institutions' descriptions and contacts and send updates.
- › Ongoing task 4: List relevant news items, once they come to be, on related subpages within 'areas' page.
- › Ongoing task 5: Keep information related to experiments up-to-date.
- › Ongoing task 6: Develop photo gallery further and keep up-to-date with new photos.
- › Ongoing task 7: Develop the website keeping inclusion - for gender, diversity and age – as the focus.

In addition to these ongoing tasks, the website will undergo a review three times annually, and its performance analysed in M18, 36 and 54 as part of the Communications & Dissemination Strategy Reviews. Web analytics allow the collection and analysis of web data, allowing us to review the website's performance and better understand who is visiting, when and where. These analytics will be used to improve the website's outreach with data on unique visitor numbers, page views, plus feedback from partners and users shared on a regular basis at project meetings.